

Metals and composites in context

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A metal is a material that, when freshly prepared, polished, or fractured, shows a lustrous appearance, and conducts electricity and heat relatively well. Metals are typically ductile (can be drawn into wires) and malleable (they can be hammered into thin sheets). These properties are the result of the metallic bond between the atoms or molecules of the metal. A metal may be a chemical element such as iron; an alloy such as stainless steel; or a molecular compound such as polymeric sulfur nitride. In physics, a metal is generally regarded as any substance capable of conducting electricity at a temperature of absolute zero. Many elements and compounds that are not normally classified as metals become metallic under high pressures. For example, the nonmetal iodine gradually becomes a metal at a pressure of between 40 and 170 thousand times atmospheric pressure. Equally, some materials regarded as metals can become nonmetals. Sodium, for example, becomes a nonmetal at pressure of just under two million times atmospheric pressure. In chemistry, two elements that would otherwise qualify (in physics) as brittle metals, arsenic and antimony, are commonly instead recognized as metalloids due to their chemistry (predominantly non-metallic for arsenic, and balanced between metallicity and non-metallicity for antimony). Around 95 of the 118 elements in the periodic table are metals (or are likely to be such) [1]. The number is inexact as the boundaries between metals, nonmetals, and metalloids fluctuate slightly due to a lack of universally accepted definitions of the categories involved. Metals are shiny and lustrous, at least when freshly prepared, polished, or fractured. Sheets of metal thicker than a few micrometers appear opaque, but gold leaf transmits green light.

The solid or liquid state of metals largely originates in the capacity of the metal atoms involved to readily lose their outer shell electrons. Broadly, the forces holding an individual atom's outer shell electrons in place are weaker than the attractive forces on the same electrons arising from interactions between the atoms in the solid or liquid metal. The electrons involved become delocalized and the atomic structure of a metal can effectively be visualized as a collection of atoms embedded in a cloud of relatively mobile electrons. This type of interaction is called a metallic bond. The strength of metallic bonds for different elemental metals reaches a maximum around the center of the transition metal series, as these elements have large numbers of delocalized electrons. Although most elemental metals have higher densities than most nonmetals, there is a wide variation in their densities, lithium being the least dense and osmium the most-dense. Magnesium, aluminum and titanium are light metals of significant commercial importance.

Metals are typically malleable and ductile, deforming under stress without cleaving. The nondirectional nature of metallic bonding is thought to contribute significantly to the ductility of most metallic solids. In contrast, in an ionic compound like table salt, when the planes of an ionic bond slide past one another, the resultant change in location shifts ions of the same charge into close proximity, resulting in the cleavage of the crystal. Such a shift is not observed in a covalently bonded crystal, such as a diamond, where fracture and crystal fragmentation occur. Reversible elastic deformation in metals can be described by Hooke's Law for restoring forces, where the stress is linearly proportional to the strain. Heat or forces larger than a metal's elastic limit may cause a permanent (irreversible) deformation, known as plastic deformation or plasticity. An applied force may be a tensile (pulling) force, a compressive (pushing) force, or a shear, bending, or torsion (twisting) force. A temperature

change may affect the movement or displacement of structural defects in the metal such as grain boundaries, point vacancies, line and screw dislocations, stacking faults and twins in both crystalline and non-crystalline metals. Internal slip, creep, and metal fatigue may ensue.

The electronic structure of metals means they are relatively good conductors of electricity. Electrons in matter can only have fixed rather than variable energy levels, and in a metal the energy levels of the electrons in its electron cloud, at least to some degree, correspond to the energy levels at which electrical conduction can occur. In a semiconductor like silicon or a nonmetal like sulfur there is an energy gap between the electrons in the substance and the energy level at which electrical conduction can occur. Consequently, semiconductors and nonmetals are relatively poor conductors. Metals are relatively good conductors of heat. The electrons in a metal's electron cloud are highly mobile and easily able to pass on heat-induced vibrational energy. The contribution of a metal's electrons to its heat capacity and thermal conductivity, and the electrical conductivity of the metal itself can be calculated from the free electron model. However, this does not take into account the detailed structure of the metal's ion lattice. Taking into account the positive potential caused by the arrangement of the ion cores enables consideration of the electronic band structure and binding energy of a metal. Various mathematical models are applicable, the simplest being the nearly free electron model.

An alloy is a substance having metallic properties and which is composed of two or more elements at least one of which is a metal. An alloy may have a variable or fixed composition. For example, gold and silver form an alloy in which the proportions of gold or silver can be freely adjusted; titanium and silicon form an alloy in which the ratio of the two components is fixed (also known as an intermetallic compound). Most pure metals are either too soft, brittle, or chemically reactive for practical use. Combining different ratios of metals as alloys modifies the properties of pure metals to produce desirable characteristics. The aim of making alloys is generally to make them less brittle, harder, resistant to corrosion, or have a more desirable color and luster. Of all the metallic alloys in use today, the alloys of iron (steel, stainless steel, alloy steel) make up the largest proportion both by quantity and commercial value [2]. Iron alloyed with various proportions of carbon gives low-carbon, mid-carbon, and high-carbon steels, with increasing carbon levels reducing ductility and toughness. The addition of silicon will produce cast irons, while the addition of chromium, nickel, and molybdenum to carbon steels results in stainless steels. Other significant metallic alloys are those of aluminum, titanium, copper, and magnesium. Copper alloys have been known since prehistory, bronze gave the Bronze Age its name, and have many applications today, most importantly in electrical wiring. The alloys of the other three metals have been developed relatively recently; due to their chemical reactivity they require electrolytic extraction processes. The alloys of aluminum, titanium, and magnesium are valued for their high strength-to-weight ratios; magnesium can also provide electromagnetic shielding. These materials are ideal for situations where high strength-to-weight ratio is more important than material cost, such as in aerospace and some automotive applications. Alloys specially designed for highly demanding applications, such as jet engines, may contain more than ten elements.

The term "ferrous" is derived from the Latin word meaning "containing iron". This can include pure iron, such as wrought iron, or an alloy such as steel. Ferrous metals are often magnetic, but not exclusively. Non-ferrous metals and alloys lack appreciable amounts of iron. While nearly all metals are malleable or ductile, a few, beryllium, chromium, manganese, gallium, and bismuth, are brittle. Arsenic and antimony, if admitted as metals, are brittle. Low values of the ratio of bulk elastic modulus to shear modulus are indicative of intrinsic brittleness. In materials science, metallurgy, and engineering, a refractory metal is a metal that is extraordinarily resistant to heat and wear. Which metals belong to this category varies; the most common definition includes niobium, molybdenum, tantalum, tungsten, and rhenium. A white metal is any of range of white-colored metals (or their alloys) with relatively low melting points. Such metals include zinc, cadmium, tin, antimony (here counted as a metal), lead, and

bismuth, some of which are quite toxic. In Britain, the fine art trade uses the term "white metal" in auction catalogues to describe foreign silver items which do not carry British Assay Office marks, but which are nonetheless understood to be silver and are priced accordingly. A heavy metal is any relatively dense metal or metalloid. More specific definitions have been proposed, but none have obtained widespread acceptance. Some heavy metals have niche uses, or are notably toxic; some are essential in trace amounts. All other metals are light metals.

A composite material (also called a composition material or shortened to composite, which is the common name) is a material which is produced from two or more constituent materials. These constituent materials have notably dissimilar chemical or physical properties and are merged to create a material with properties unlike the individual elements [3]. Within the finished structure, the individual elements remain separate and distinct, distinguishing composites from mixtures and solid solutions. Typical engineered composite materials include: reinforced concrete and masonry, reinforced plastics, such as fiber-reinforced polymer or fiberglass, ceramic matrix composites (composite ceramic and metal matrices), metal matrix composites, and other advanced composite materials.

There are various reasons where new material can be favored. Typical examples include materials which are less expensive, lighter, stronger or more durable when compared with common materials. Composite materials are created from individual materials. These individual materials are known as constituent materials, and there are two main categories of it. One is the matrix (binder) and the other reinforcement. A portion of each kind is needed at least. The reinforcement receives support from the matrix as the matrix surrounds the reinforcement and maintains its relative positions. The properties of the matrix are improved as the reinforcements impart their exceptional physical and mechanical properties. The mechanical properties become unavailable from the individual constituent materials by synergism. At the same time, the designer of the product or structure receives options to choose an optimum combination from the variety of matrix and strengthening materials. To shape the engineered composites, it must be formed. The reinforcement is placed onto the mold surface or into the mold cavity. Before or after this, the matrix can be introduced to the reinforcement. The matrix undergoes a melding event which sets the part shape necessarily. This melding event can happen in several ways, depending upon the matrix nature, such as solidification from the melted state for a thermoplastic polymer matrix composite or chemical polymerization for a thermoset polymer matrix.

According to the requirements of end-item design, various methods of molding can be used. The natures of the chosen matrix and reinforcement are the key factors influencing the methodology. The gross quantity of material to be made is another main factor. To support high capital investments for rapid and automated manufacturing technology, vast quantities can be used. Cheaper capital investments but higher labor and tooling expenses at a correspondingly slower rate assists the small production quantities. Many commercially produced composites use a polymer matrix material often called a resin solution. There are many different polymers available depending upon the starting raw ingredients. There are several broad categories, each with numerous variations. The most common are known as polyester, vinyl ester, epoxy, phenolic, polyimide, polyamide, polypropylene, and others. Normally, the fabrication of composite includes wetting, mixing or saturating the reinforcement with the matrix. The matrix is then induced to bind together (with heat or a chemical reaction) into a rigid structure. Usually, the operation is done in an open or closed forming mold. However, the order and ways of introducing the constituents alters considerably. Composites fabrication is achieved by a wide variety of methods. The reinforcing and matrix materials are merged, compacted, and cured (processed) within a mold to undergo a melding event. The part shape is fundamentally set after the melding event. However, under particular process conditions, it can deform. The melding event for a thermoset polymer matrix material is a curing reaction that is caused by the possibility of extra heat or chemical reactivity such as an organic peroxide. The melding event for a thermoplastic polymeric matrix

material is a solidification from the melted state. The melding event for a metal matrix material such as titanium foil is a fusing at high pressure and a temperature near the melting point.

Usually, the composite's physical properties are not isotropic in nature. But they are typically anisotropic [4]. For instance, the composite panel's stiffness will usually depend upon the orientation of the applied forces and moments. The composite's strength is bounded by two loading conditions. If both the fibers and matrix are aligned parallel to the loading direction, the deformation of both phases will be the same. This iso-strain condition provides the upper bound for composite strength, and is determined by the rule of mixtures. The lower bound is dictated by the iso-stress condition, in which the fibers and matrix are oriented perpendicularly to the loading direction. The iso-strain condition implies that under an applied load, both phases experience the same strain but will feel different stress. Comparatively, under iso-stress conditions both phases will feel the same stress but the strains will differ between each phase. Though composite stiffness is maximized when fibers are aligned with the loading direction, so is the possibility of fiber tensile fracture, assuming the tensile strength exceeds that of the matrix. The majority of commercial composites are formed with random dispersion and orientation of the strengthening fibers, in which case the composite Young's modulus will fall between the iso-strain and iso-stress bounds. However, in applications where the strength-to-weight ratio is engineered to be as high as possible, fiber alignment may be tightly controlled. Panel stiffness is also dependent on the design of the panel. For instance, the fiber reinforcement and matrix used, the method of panel build, thermoset versus thermoplastic, and type of weave.

In contrast to composites, isotropic materials, in standard wrought forms, possess the same stiffness typically despite the directional orientation of the applied forces and moments. The relationship between forces-moments and strains-curvatures for an isotropic material can be described with the following material properties: Young's Modulus, the Shear Modulus and the Poisson's ratio, in relatively simple mathematical relationships. For the anisotropic material, it needs the mathematics of a second-order tensor and up to 21 material property constants. For the special case of orthogonal isotropy, there are three distinct material property constants for each of Young's Modulus, Shear Modulus and Poisson's ratio, a total of 9 constants to express the relationship between forces-moments and strains-curvatures. In general, particle reinforcement is strengthening the composites less than fiber reinforcement. It is used to enhance the stiffness of the composites while increasing the strength and the toughness. Because of their mechanical properties, they are used in applications in which wear resistance is required. For example, hardness of cement can be increased by reinforcing gravel particles, drastically. Particle reinforcement a highly advantageous method of tuning mechanical properties of materials since it is very easy implement while being low cost. In general, continuous fiber reinforcement is implemented by incorporating a fiber as the strong phase into a weak phase, matrix. The reason for the popularity of fiber usage is materials with extraordinary strength can be obtained in their fiber form. Non-metallic fibers are usually showing a very high strength to density ratio compared to metal fibers because of the covalent nature of their bonds. The most famous example of this is carbon fibers that have many applications extending from sports gear to protective equipment to space industries. The stress on the composite can be expressed in terms of the volume fraction of the fiber and the matrix. Although the stress-strain behavior of fiber composites can only be determined by testing, there is an expected trend, three stages of the stress-strain curve. The first stage is the region of the stress-strain curve where both fiber and the matrix are elastically deformed.

In reality, the derivative of stress with respect to strain is not always returning the modulus because of the binding interaction between the fiber and matrix. The strength of the interaction between these two phases can result in changes in the mechanical properties of the composite. The compatibility of the fiber and matrix is a measure of internal stress. The covalently bonded high strength fibers experience mostly elastic deformation before the fracture since the plastic deformation can happen due

to dislocation motion. Whereas, metallic fibers have more space to plastically deform, so their composites exhibit a third stage where both fiber and the matrix are plastically deforming. Metallic fibers have many applications to work at cryogenic temperatures that is one of the advantages of composites with metal fibers over nonmetallic. A change in the angle between the applied stress and fiber orientation will affect the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced composites, especially the tensile strength. This angle can be used to predict the dominant tensile fracture mechanism. Anisotropy in the tensile strength of fiber reinforced composites can be removed by randomly orienting the fiber directions within the material. It sacrifices the ultimate strength in the aligned direction for an overall, isotropically strengthened material.

Shock, impact, or repeated cyclic stresses can provoke the laminate to separate at the interface between two layers, a condition known as delamination. Individual fibers can separate from the matrix, for example, fiber pull-out. Composites can fail on the macroscopic or microscopic scale [5]. Compression failures can happen at both the macro scale or at each individual reinforcing fiber in compression buckling. Tension failures can be net section failures of the part or degradation of the composite at a microscopic scale where one or more of the layers in the composite failure in tension of the matrix or failure of the bond between the matrix and fibers. Some composites are brittle and possess little reserve strength beyond the initial onset of failure while others may have large deformations and have reserve energy absorbing capacity past the onset of damage. The distinctions in fibers and matrices that are available and the mixtures that can be made with blends leave a very broad range of properties that can be designed into a composite structure. Composites have relatively poor bearing strength compared to metals. Composites are tested before and after construction to assist in predicting and preventing failures. Pre-construction testing may adopt finite element analysis for ply-by-ply analysis of curved surfaces and predicting wrinkling, crimping and dimpling of composites.

Concrete is the most common artificial composite material of all and typically consists of loose stones (aggregate) held with a matrix of cement. Concrete is an inexpensive material, and will not compress or shatter even under quite a large compressive force. However, concrete cannot survive tensile loading. Therefore, to give concrete the ability to resist being stretched, steel bars, which can resist high stretching (tensile) forces, are often added to concrete to form reinforced concrete. Fiber-reinforced polymers include carbon fiber reinforced polymer and glass-reinforced plastic. If classified by matrix then there are thermoplastic composites, short fiber thermoplastics, long fiber thermoplastics or long fiber-reinforced thermoplastics. There are numerous thermoset composites, including paper composite panels. Many advanced thermoset polymer matrix systems usually incorporate aramid fiber and carbon fiber in an epoxy resin matrix. Shape memory polymer composites are high-performance composites, formulated using fiber or fabric reinforcements and shape memory polymer resin as the matrix. Since a shape memory polymer resin is used as the matrix, these composites have the ability to be easily manipulated into various configurations when they are heated above their activation temperatures and will exhibit high strength and stiffness at lower temperatures. They can also be reheated and reshaped repeatedly without losing their material properties. These composites are ideal for applications such as lightweight, rigid, deployable structures; rapid manufacturing; and dynamic reinforcement. High strain composites are another type of high-performance composites that are designed to perform in a high deformation setting and are often used in deployable systems where structural flexing is advantageous. Although high strain composites exhibit many similarities to shape memory polymers, their performance is generally dependent on the fiber layout as opposed to the resin content of the matrix. Composites can also use metal fibers reinforcing other metals, as in metal matrix composites or ceramic matrix composites. Ceramic matrix composites are built primarily for fracture toughness, not for strength. Another class of composite materials involve woven fabric composite consisting of longitudinal and transverse laced yarns. Woven

fabric composites are flexible as they are in form of fabric.

Fiber-reinforced plastic is a composite material made of a polymer matrix reinforced with fibers. The fibers are usually glass (in fiberglass), carbon (in carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer), aramid, or basalt. The polymer is usually an epoxy, vinyl ester, or polyester thermosetting plastic, though phenol formaldehyde resins are still in use. A polymer is generally manufactured by step-growth polymerization or addition polymerization. When combined with various agents to enhance or in any way alter the material properties of polymers, the result is referred to as a plastic. Composite plastics refers to those types of plastics that result from bonding two or more homogeneous materials with different material properties to derive a final product with certain desired material and mechanical properties. Fiber-reinforced plastics are a category of composite plastics that specifically use fiber materials to mechanically enhance the strength and elasticity of plastics [6]. The original plastic material without fiber reinforcement is known as the matrix or binding agent. The matrix is a tough but relatively weak plastic that is reinforced by stronger stiffer reinforcing filaments or fibers. The extent that strength and elasticity are enhanced in a fiber-reinforced plastic depends on the mechanical properties of both the fiber and matrix, their volume relative to one another, and the fiber length and orientation within the matrix. Reinforcement of the matrix occurs by definition when the fiber-reinforced plastic material exhibits increased strength or elasticity relative to the strength and elasticity of the matrix alone. Fiber-reinforced plastic involves two distinct processes, the first is the process whereby the fibrous material is manufactured and formed, the second is the process whereby fibrous materials are bonded with the matrix during molding.

Fiber-reinforced plastic allows the alignment of the glass fibers of thermoplastics to suit specific design programs. Specifying the orientation of reinforcing fibers can increase the strength and resistance to deformation of the polymer. Glass reinforced polymers are strongest and most resistive to deforming forces when the polymers fibers are parallel to the force being exerted, and are weakest when the fibers are perpendicular. Thus, this ability is at once both an advantage or a limitation depending on the context of use. Weak spots of perpendicular fibers can be used for natural hinges and connections, but can also lead to material failure when production processes fail to properly orient the fibers parallel to expected forces. When forces are exerted perpendicular to the orientation of fibers, the strength and elasticity of the polymer is less than the matrix alone. In cast resin components made of glass reinforced polymers, the orientation of fibers can be oriented in two-dimensional and three-dimensional weaves. This means that when forces are possibly perpendicular to one orientation, they are parallel to another orientation; this eliminates the potential for weak spots in the polymer.

A thermoset polymer matrix material, or engineering grade thermoplastic polymer matrix material, must meet certain requirements in order to first be suitable for FRPs and ensure a successful reinforcement of itself. The matrix must be able to properly saturate, and preferably bond chemically with the fiber reinforcement for maximum adhesion within a suitable curing period. The matrix must also completely envelop the fibers to protect them from cuts and notches that would reduce their strength, and to transfer forces to the fibers. The fibers must also be kept separate from each other so that if failure occurs it is localized as much as possible, and if failure occurs the matrix must also de-bond from the fiber for similar reasons. Finally, the matrix should be of a plastic that remains chemically and physically stable during and after the reinforcement and molding processes. To be suitable as reinforcement material, fiber additives must increase the tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the matrix and meet the following conditions; fibers must exceed critical fiber content; the strength and rigidity of fibers itself must exceed the strength and rigidity of the matrix alone; and there must be optimum bonding between fibers and matrix.

In materials science, ceramic matrix composites are a subgroup of composite materials and a subgroup of ceramics. They consist of ceramic fibers embedded in a ceramic matrix. The fibers and the

matrix both can consist of any ceramic material, whereby carbon and carbon fibers can also be regarded as a ceramic material. The motivation to develop ceramic matrix composites was to overcome the problems associated with the conventional technical ceramics like alumina, silicon carbide, aluminum nitride, silicon nitride or zirconia, they fracture easily under mechanical or thermo-mechanical loads because of cracks initiated by small defects or scratches. The crack resistance is very low, as in glass. To increase the crack resistance or fracture toughness, particles were embedded into the matrix. However, the improvement was limited, and the products have found application only in some ceramic cutting tools. So far only the integration of long multi-strand fibers has drastically increased the crack resistance, elongation and thermal shock resistance, and resulted in several new applications. The reinforcements used in ceramic matrix composites serve to enhance the fracture toughness of the combined material system while still taking advantage of the inherent high strength and Young's modulus of the ceramic matrix. The most common reinforcement embodiment is a continuous-length ceramic fiber, with an elastic modulus that is typically somewhat lower than the matrix. The functional role of this fiber is to increase the ceramic matrix composite stress for the progress of micro-cracks through the matrix, thereby increasing the energy expended during crack propagation; and then when thru-thickness cracks begin to form across the ceramic matrix composite at higher stress, to bridge these cracks without fracturing, thereby providing the ceramic matrix composite with a high ultimate tensile strength. In this way, ceramic fiber reinforcements not only increase the composite structure's initial resistance to crack propagation but also allow the ceramic matrix composite to avoid abrupt brittle failure that is characteristic of monolithic ceramics. This behavior is distinct from the behavior of ceramic fibers in polymer matrix composites and metal matrix composites, where the fibers typically fracture before the matrix due to the higher failure strain capabilities of these matrices.

In materials science, a metal matrix composite is a composite material with fibers or particles dispersed in a metallic matrix, such as copper, aluminum, or steel. The secondary phase is typically a ceramic (such as alumina or silicon carbide) or another metal. They are typically classified according to the type of reinforcement: short discontinuous fibers, continuous fibers, or particulates. When at least three materials are present, it is called a hybrid composite. Metal matrix composites can have much higher strength-to-weight ratios, stiffness, and ductility than traditional materials, so they are often used in demanding applications [7]. Metal matrix composites typically have lower thermal and electrical conductivity and poor resistance to radiation, limiting their use in the very harshest environments. Metal matrix composites are made by dispersing a reinforcing material into a metal matrix. The reinforcement surface can be coated to prevent a chemical reaction with the matrix. For example, carbon fibers are commonly used in aluminum matrix to synthesize composites showing low density and high strength. However, carbon reacts with aluminum to generate a brittle and water-soluble compound on the surface of the fiber. To prevent this reaction, the carbon fibers are coated with nickel or titanium boride. The matrix is the monolithic material into which the reinforcement is embedded, and is completely continuous. This means that there is a path through the matrix to any point in the material, unlike two materials sandwiched together. In structural applications, the matrix is usually a lighter metal such as aluminum, magnesium, or titanium, and provides a complete support for the reinforcement. In high-temperature applications, cobalt and cobalt-nickel alloy matrices are common.

The reinforcement material is embedded into a matrix. The reinforcement does not always serve a purely structural task (reinforcing the compound), but is also used to change physical properties such as wear resistance, friction coefficient, or thermal conductivity. The reinforcement can be either continuous or discontinuous. Discontinuous metal matrix composites can be isotropic and can be worked with standard metalworking techniques, such as extrusion, forging, or rolling. In addition, they may be machined using conventional techniques, but commonly would need the use of polycrystalline diamond tooling. Continuous reinforcement uses monofilament wires or fibers such as carbon fiber or

silicon carbide. Because the fibers are embedded into the matrix in a certain direction, the result is an anisotropic structure in which the alignment of the material affects its strength. One of the first metal matrix composites used boron filament as reinforcement. Discontinuous reinforcement uses "whiskers", short fibers, or particles. The most common reinforcing materials in this category are alumina and silicon carbide. Metal matrix composites are fabricated at elevated temperatures, which is an essential condition for diffusion bonding of the fiber-matrix interface. Later on, when they are cooled down to the ambient temperature, residual stresses are generated in the composite due to the mismatch between the coefficients of the metal matrix and fiber. The manufacturing residual stresses significantly influence the mechanical behavior of the metal matrix composites in all loading conditions. In some cases, thermal residual stresses are high enough to initiate plastic deformation within the matrix during the manufacturing process. In comparison with conventional polymer matrix composites, metal matrix composites are resistant to fire, can operate in wider range of temperatures, do not absorb moisture, have better electrical and thermal conductivity, are resistant to radiation damage, and do not display outgassing [8]. On the other hand, metal matrix composites tend to be more expensive, the fiber-reinforced materials may be difficult to fabricate, and the available experience in use is limited.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] R.W. Cahn, Combining metals and sciences: Ways of investigating intermetallics. *Intermetallics*, Volume 6, Issues 7-8, 1998, Pages 563-566.
- [2] S. Gialanella and L. Lutterotti. On the measure of order in alloys. *Progress in Materials Science*, Volume 42, Issues 1-4, 1997, Pages 125-133.
- [3] R.R. Volkas and G.C. Joshi. Supersymmetric composite models. *Physics Reports*, Volume 159, Issue 6, 1988, Pages 303-386.
- [4] E. Fitzer. The future of carbon-carbon composites. *Carbon*, Volume 25, Issue 2, 1987, Pages 163-190.
- [5] L. Dobrzynski. Interface response theory of discrete composite systems. *Surface Science Reports*, Volume 6, Issue 3, 1986, Pages 119-157.
- [6] G. Kretsis. A review of the tensile, compressive, flexural and shear properties of hybrid fibre-reinforced plastics. *Composites*, Volume 18, Issue 1, 1987, Pages 13-23.
- [7] Z.X. Guo and B. Derby. Solid-state fabrication and interfaces of fibre reinforced metal matrix composites. *Progress in Materials Science*, Volume 39, Issues 4-5, 1995, Pages 411-495.
- [8] L. Parrini and R. Schaller. Thermal stresses in metal matrix composites studied by internal friction. *Acta Materialia*, Volume 44, Issue 12, 1996, Pages 4881-4888.